

Supplementary material:

Explanations of ICD 10 codes:

I85.0 - Esophageal varices with bleeding

K22.6 - Gastro-esophageal laceration-hemorrhage syndrome

K22.8 - Other specified diseases of esophagus

K25.0 - Gastric ulcer: acute with hemorrhage

K25.2 - Gastric ulcer: acute with both hemorrhage and perforation

K25.4 - Gastric ulcer: chronic or unspecified with hemorrhage

K25.6 - Gastric ulcer: chronic or unspecified with both hemorrhage and perforation

K26.0 - Duodenal ulcer: acute with hemorrhage

K26.2 - Duodenal ulcer: acute with both hemorrhage and perforation

K26.4 - Duodenal ulcer: chronic or unspecified with hemorrhage

K26.6 - Duodenal ulcer: chronic or unspecified with both hemorrhage and perforation

K27.0 - Peptic ulcer, site unspecified: acute with hemorrhage

K27.2 - Peptic ulcer, site unspecified: acute with both hemorrhage and perforation

K27.4 - Peptic ulcer, site unspecified: chronic or unspecified with hemorrhage

K27.6 - Peptic ulcer, site unspecified: chronic or unspecified with both hemorrhage and perforation

K28.0 - Gastrojejunal ulcer: acute with hemorrhage

K28.2 - Gastrojejunal ulcer: acute with both hemorrhage and perforation

K28.4 - Gastrojejunal ulcer: chronic or unspecified with hemorrhage

K28.6 - Gastrojejunal ulcer: chronic or unspecified with both hemorrhage and perforation

K29.0 - Acute hemorrhagic gastritis

K62.5 - Hemorrhage of anus and rectum

K92.0 - Hematemesis

K92.1 - Melaena

K92.2 - Gastrointestinal hemorrhage, unspecified

K70.3 - Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver

K71.7 - Toxic liver disease with fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver

K74.3 - Primary biliary cirrhosis

K74.4 - Secondary biliary cirrhosis

K74.5 - Biliary cirrhosis, unspecified

K74.6 - Other and unspecified cirrhosis of liver

Figure S1: Search results of the medical records of patients hospitalized in the department from August 2015 to December 2018.

